

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan**

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring. It is funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling needs and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OTF	Outreach Task Force
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SoA	State of the Art
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modelling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth, and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. One of the main goals also of RAMONES is to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

Additionally, one of the key tasks of the project is to increase local citizens as well as stakeholders and policymakers' awareness and involvement based on diverse dissemination, communication, and outreach activities, through scientific evidence and FAIR data principles¹. RAMONES is adopting several intense dissemination and communication strategies towards raising public awareness and attracting citizen involvement through multiple identified channels and target groups.

The main aim of this deliverable is to clearly define the project's "Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation" goals, and to describe the respective plan to that end for the entire project duration. The activities carried out, resources and achievements will be presented in future reports within the same work package.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FAIR_data

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The dissemination strategy definition provides the outline for the activities to be undertaken within the dissemination task, setting out the dissemination goals for the project's duration. The dissemination plan will be regularly updated and will include the specific actions necessary to achieve the strategy goals. The type of dissemination activities included in the plan is defined according to each specific target group to be reached each time. Moreover, a variety of complementing and interrelated dissemination material and activities are planned for the project's dissemination task to reach the maximum amount of what was projected on the DoA (Description of the Art) communities in the most cost-efficient and at the same time appealing way.

Dissemination is at the forefront of both professional and general public levels. On the one hand, the most relevant scientific and technical results achieved within RAMONES will be published in international refereed journals or conferences and will be presented in international events or workshops. On the other hand, the related communities (and the general public) will be informed about the project concepts and achievements from the dissemination material and communication channels that are foreseen within the planned project activities. In any case, defining and launching a dedicated website, included also in WP5, is the valuable channel to reach the widest range of public.

The strategy will be strongly based on the concept of Key Performance Indicator (KPI). Success indicators within each KPI will help to evaluate the success criteria for that particular KPI. The KPIs proposed in this deliverable will be highly oriented towards the nature of the dissemination activities.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document is part of Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular to Task T5.3 on Raising Citizens Awareness, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities. The document outlines the vision, strategy, and a plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes and baseline dissemination material related to the RAMONES project.

The strategy is initially released as a draft and will be updated as the understanding of the opportunities in context grows, and this is a very important caveat of this early release of this document. This plan lays out the roadmap to maximize the output from the project effort in the direction of:

- (i) bringing its results to the wider and most appropriate audience that will be interested or motivated in exploiting or uptaking it, and
- (ii) informing key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals at medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies and engaging them into project's activities to adopt and establish strong synergies.

The plan will refine the project strategy, with respect to overall objective, scope, and targeted stakeholders (and the related sub-objectives and means for each target) and then lay out the resource allocation plan and key points in time for communication activities, dissemination, citizen awareness, stakeholder engagement, liaison activities and knowledge transfer.

1.2 Structure of the document

From this point, the current document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

1. **Objectives and approach:** Introduction to the objectives to raise awareness, communication, dissemination, outreach, engagement, and exploitation plans and the relevant approaches for consequent development.
2. **Communication and dissemination strategy.** As a preliminary step, a raise of awareness, communication, dissemination, outreach, and engagement strategy is set, first considering the consolidation of the project identity, the target audience definition as a prior step to organize the key messages to communicate to the audience and the engagement plan for the stakeholders.
3. **Methodology.** The development of the methodology section is the main part of the document, starting with the communication and dissemination principles before continuing with the process for the generation of contents and the tools, resources and

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means to carry out dissemination activities, both at a wide range and for ecosystem scope. Lastly, the project resources for partners are presented.

- 4. **Organization.** The organization section presents the coordination model, the roles of the project partners and the monitoring and evaluation method, including the definition of KPIs.
- 5. **Planning.** Finally, an activity timeline is presented.

2. Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES communication, dissemination, citizen awareness, outreach, and engagement & exploitation plan and how they will be implemented are described in the following table:

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination, Citizen Awareness, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation Plan approach.

Type of Activity	RAMONES Objectives	Means and Activities
Communication	1. Increase RAMONES visibility in terms of activities and outcomes; receive valuable feedback	Communication effort aiming at the targeted multiple audience beyond RAMONES community; Exploit feedback strengthening potentials and exploitation
	2. Inform Society and communities / enhance the engagement with stakeholders	Communicate project outcomes to a broad, diverse audience. Targeted communication efforts towards target groups (radioactivity, environmental, marine robotics, social scientists, analysts) and relevant stakeholders.
Dissemination	3. Position RAMONES as a top-rank EIC project and in Environmental Intelligence European projects ecosystem	Dense dissemination activities linked to the offered project outcomes to promote them during their operational phase within the considered sectors and Environmental Intelligence community.
	4. Boost networking and engagement strategy of the RAMONES results	Targeted and synchronized dissemination, communication, exploitation, and communities' engagement activities aiming towards all target audiences and policymakers.
Raise Awareness	5. Share knowledge of the offered methodologies and instrumentation	Project development along with communication and dissemination activities and targeted communities' engagement aiming at primary target audiences.

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	6. Raise awareness and demonstrate how RAMONES outcomes (methodologies and instrumentation) can cater to the needs of the stakeholders and of the communities	Communication efforts along with carefully designed activities for maximizing impact including hands-on training of several primary targeted audiences.
Outreach	7. Engage large audiences and bring knowledge and expertise from RAMONES objectives and outcomes to the relevant communities, policy makers and stakeholders, as well as the general public.	Outreach activities will be accomplished via approaches specialized to audiences in question, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, datathons/hackathons always with the appropriate communication material
Engagement & Exploitation	8. Linking to the most possible communities and stakeholders with possible adoption of RAMONES outcomes	Sequential approach to relevant communities and policy makers/stakeholders, relevant national European projects from the early stages of the project for the best possible adoption of the project offerings. Laying out synergies with projects, task forces, relevant organizations and other initiatives that can be materialized as formal (via MOUs or other agreements) and informal joint activities.

In particular, the main objectives are:

- to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work.
- to maximize the impactful visibility of the project's work and achievements.
- to engage stakeholders that can support project sustainability through both update and feedback and can further empower the vision around EIC and Environmental Intelligence goals.
- to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating esp. in the H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

Its achievement will be led by the Outreach Task Force (OTF) (see Grant Agreement, RAMONES Deliverable D1.2 “*Project procedures and instruments, project collaboration and management procedure*”), with the support of the Project Management Board and the participation of all project members according to their knowledge, their area of expertise, and their networking. The achievement goals must be reached in a collaborative way under a common strategy; thus, some important tasks of the Outreach Task force (OTF) will be to provide project members

with the main resources to facilitate its activities and to encourage the members to work together.

The approach can be summarized under the following 7 conditions:

- **Announce RAMONES to the scientific community:** it needs to properly explain the RAMONES's vision and strategy, identify key target groups (targeted interest groups in research, business, and technology) and define content and channels for each target.
- **Partners, the first believers, first users and first promoters.** It is necessary to gain the engagement of the partners (by means of internal communication) and to take advantage of each partner's knowledge and contacts to boost their best contributions. A recurrent task of enhancing and sharing synergies will drive to the best achievements.
- **Understand the real needs of the target groups (Research groups, other RIs stakeholders, scientific groups, technology providers, policy makers/stakeholders, general public):** to achieve a deep understanding of real needs is necessary to enable and promote 2-way communication channels.
- **Tune the offer:** to define values, services, and solutions, we need to transfer to the offering the identified needs.
- **Boost the demand:** By means of close access to research, public communities and stakeholder needs, identification of the communication messages, and dissemination of content and benefits of RAMONES outcomes
- **Knowledge hub:** Content and knowledge repository implies coordination of any news and content between project partners, and its later dissemination and storage.
- **Measurement & Control:** No achievement can be made without its measurement and control, both for reporting purposes and for best possible results tactics to strengthen the recurrent collaboration among all the partners.

3. Communication & Dissemination Strategy

3.1 Project identity

To get a recognizable RAMONES brand, a project identity and graphic charter have been developed. This brand image which will be used for any RAMONES communication and dissemination actions, both internal and external scope, is presented below:

Figure 1. RAMONES official logo (in black background; additional colors are available).

The project identity relates to the appearance and visibility of a project for any stakeholder and applies to any document or resource created). This includes the logo, the color palette, the typography, and page compositions. Its application is required for any document (project deliverables, presentation, leaflets, brochures, etc), the web site or the social media banners. A set of templates and a set of styles for different purposes have been created and shared with all the project partners to homogenize the project outputs. In addition, any product or reusable material related to the RAMONES project (posters, leaflets, banners, notebooks, pens, etc) will be designed incorporating the logo and RAMONES patterns, whenever possible.

Changes on the brand image are possible during the first months of the project through consultation and internal agreement among partners.

3.2 Target audience

As RAMONES will develop methodologies and instrumentation towards specific communities and stakeholders' current needs and requirements, the target groups have already been identified in the DoA. They are segmented from their field of activity (sector) as well as the different profiles identification.

3.2.1 Segmentation analysis from a field of activity perspective

Based on the specific goals of the call stating that **improvement of quality of life and citizen involvement** should be fully preserved, RAMONES aims to enable continuous in situ monitoring of underwater radioactivity, contributing to environmental sustainability and the **improvement in the citizens' quality of life** by assessing radioactivity related risks, including geohazards (e.g. earthquakes and volcanic activity) and anthropogenic events. With regards to

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citizen involvement, RAMONES endorses gender equality and research ethics while contributing to science education, increasing citizen awareness, and encouraging engagement of stakeholders and the public to maximize the relevance of the research with societal needs. This will be achieved by broadening out dissemination, communication and outreach activities to multiple thematic sectors, such as radioactivity studies, robotics, mobile marine radioactivity-sensing solutions, natural hazards, forecasting systems and ICT sectors, where we can identify the different range of research and academics communities and RI stakeholders as well as the communities of the general public that RAMONES will address:

- For the Radioactivity sector: nuclear/particle/radiation physicists, health physicists, geologists, chemists, geoscientists, geospatial scientists, oil & gas engineers, submarine geohazards, environmental and marine scientists, energy and power sector, ecologists, civil protection, coastal policy, remote sensing, navigation and positioning, spectral imaging, electrical and electronic engineering, business analytics
- Mobile Marine Radioactivity Sensing: ocean engineers, marine robotic engineers and specialists, autonomous underwater vehicle engineers and businesses, ocean telecom experts, marine remote sensing specialists.
- For the Environmental Intelligence sector: Environmental scientists in academia, international organizations and business sectors; high-tech interdisciplinary companies; governmental bodies; standardization bodies and committees; national and international policy-makers.
- Forecasting Systems Engineers, Econometricians, Systems Designers, Operational Researchers.
- For ICT sector: engineers in a wide range of activities such as marine robotics, supporting instrument development, marine telecommunications, hardware/software architects, sensor/imaging/navigation/robotic experts capture, management and analysis, machine learning.

This segmentation will allow us to identify the best WP thematic area from which to know, understand and connect with the needs of the above different communities

3.2.2 Segmentation analysis from a profile/needs' perspective

In addition to the sector perspective, it is needed to set the profile of stakeholders to understand the real needs and potential engagement with the project, as well as the key message definition to reach them in the best way.

The preliminary segmentation considers the following profiles, defining their needs and potential connection to RAMONES:

- *Researchers*: Individual researchers are easier to mobilize on a personal basis through project offerings, support for penetration into scientific communities and provide valuable feedback. They also provide gateways to larger groups and other disciplines.
- *Research groups*: Research groups are the intended main target group of the project, for reusing and interweaving the modelling, simulations, and data offerings to be generated. They are a major provider of validation information and feedback, as well as the drivers of interdisciplinary research targeted by the project.
- *Academic institutes*: Academic institutes can form an application space where RAMONES solutions (methodologies, forecasting algorithms, possibly instrumentation architecture) can be utilized in the field of education, in labs and lesson courses.
- *Data scientists*: Data scientists can significantly enrich the project results regarding data offerings adding to research potential, value chain and business and sustainability opportunities.
- *Open Access/Open Science Initiatives*: Open access/Open Science initiatives provide guidance, support, validation, and assets that can be reused in the context of the Project.
- *Business SMEs*: Since innovative outcomes are provided by RAMONES, SMEs and providing services on top of RAMONES results are one of the best options for creating value chains on top of project's offerings and towards long-term sustainability targets.
- *Governmental Entities, Local Representatives and Other Public Sector Bodies*: Governance and policy making is an essential target group of the project, and substantially adds to the sustainability outlook.
- *Funders*: Funders' awareness is a great means of validation and is also a suggested part of the project's outcomes.
- *General Public*: the project is also addressed to the general public, including any audience not mentioned above, such as journalists, students, NGOs, or the society in a broader sense.

3.3 Key messages

The messages to generate must be tailored to the individual segments, highlighting the specific benefits of the project for each one, to favor its reception. In addition, the language and context must be aligned with the perspective of their field of activity exposed above.

The main benefits to expose are the following:

Table 2. Key messages according to targeted audiences.

Profile	Benefits to communicate
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broadening the user base ● Indirect raising of awareness ● Enabling new (interdisciplinary) research opportunities ● Availability of enhanced tools for research ● Facilitation of focus on core activities ● New ways of collaboration
Research groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broadening user base ● Indirect raising of awareness ● Provisioning of structured feedback ● Identification and enabling of new (interdisciplinary) research opportunities ● Availability of enhanced tools for research ● Facilitation of focus on core activities
Academic institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broadening user base ● Expanding business opportunities ● New opportunities of collaboration ● Availability of channels for promotion and dissemination
Data scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase of data offerings ● New opportunities for research ● Expanding business opportunities
Open Access / Open Science Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project awareness support ● Validation and feedback acquisition ● Embracing open science ● Validation and feedback acquisition ● Availability of new channels for promotion and dissemination ● New ways of collaboration
Business SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Empowering of sustainability options ● New business opportunities ● Access to new fields and ecosystems
Governance & Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expansion to new business cases ● Widening of sustainability options ● Empowerment of research

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● New opportunities for helping the collaboration, facilitating the focus on strategic / core sectors● Availability of new KPIs
Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Validation and feedback● Amplification of outreach● Supporting/validating sustainability
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Increase the value of project and individual partners● General information according to transparency principles

3.4 Engagement plan

The dissemination activities are led by the OTF, but all the partners are expected to support the best achievements. The aim is to maximize their knowledge, experience and networking concerning each specific area of their expertise, both in different fields (radiation detectors, underwater research, marine engineering, forecasting, etc.) and countries. Working together, the range and impact of any dissemination action will be empowered to its highest degree.

The key action is to consolidate an engagement plan that will drive all the project members to actively participate as much as possible in the dissemination activities.

The following aspects are considered key, and will be reviewed and enhanced for the full project life:

- Best practices guide: Development of a guide of best practices to encourage the partners to take advantage of available resources (RAMONES website, partners' websites, digital social platforms, reusable material, etc.) to boost the results of the dissemination activities.

The guidelines will be dynamically developed, presented, and shared on the project platform. These documents can also be generated as a response to a requirement, as well as considering a specific need of the project development.

- Team building: Keeping partners aligned with common goals will allow us to be synchronized in the activities, sharing content, and produced material, sharing learnings, saving efforts, and acting in a similar way in different fields, contexts and countries.

This will also drive the RAMONES to better identify and manage any potential risk or contingency, allocating resources and solutions as best suits.

The project meetings, the internal mailings, social platforms, and digital channels including the web site will be appropriate to get it.

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- Fields of knowledge: the project involves many contents from different fields of knowledge, which is necessary to allow an easy understanding of all the stakeholders and even the members of the consortium.

Some activities and generation of content need to be performed by a particular partner (specifically those concerning research fields) to identify, produce, and validate its suitability and quality and to suggest the best research and domain specific channels and scenarios to disseminate. The impact on the target audience is expected to be higher if carried out by a recognized player in the sector.

- Sharing achievements: Any achievement is a great success that is worth communicating and sharing among all project members, allowing it to be integrated into all the work package activities and get feedback.

The project meetings, the use of internal mail and the digital channels will support the above process. For external scope, the News section of the RAMONES website and the social channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Youtube) are undoubtedly the best way to propagate good news in a timely fashion.

4. Methodology

4.1 Raise Awareness

All dissemination activities should follow some important principles:

- Respect IPR of all partners
- Respect the work of all partners
- Ensure the proper reference of all relevant parties whose work is directly or indirectly mentioned in the proposed publication
- Follow transparent procedures
- Respect confidential results and results for which commercial issues arise
- Avoid overlapping or duplication of dissemination events
- Clearly distinguish between results suitable for dissemination and exploitable results
- Target the right audience
- Always mention the RAMONES project
- Always follow the dissemination procedures
- All content must comply with the good practices and style books about European recommendations and ethics
- GDPR policy compliance, according to the definition provided by the WP5 group.

4.2 Communication

Dissemination and communication activities are carried out on two fronts: (i) at a broad level, containing mainly general contents for any kind of audience, and (ii) the ecosystem level, considering people involved in research or technology fields.

Firstly, wide range dissemination aims to make RAMONES known to any undetermined public as much as possible. The main instruments explaining the project goals, the work and its context, the benefits and the achievements of RAMONES are presented below. In any case, any of them can also be useful for stakeholders. This is achieved via the following fora and platforms:

4.2.1 Website

A dedicated portal for RAMONES (<https://ramones-project.eu/>) is one of the most important channels to promote the dissemination and communication of the work performed, results and impact of ongoing project activities. The website is designed at the beginning of the activities and will be updated throughout its whole life, including updated information about the project and the consortium, news, achievements, events, downloadable material, and any relevant content of interest.

The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the project and its results by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the project community. The specific goals of this dissemination and communication channel are the following:

- To be a reference point of knowledge about the project, including scope and framework, consortium, project organization and activities.
- To be a content hub updated with the main reports, documents, and any produced material concerning RAMONES.
- To be a reference point for dissemination and engagement, both with its own content and through connections to other sites or platforms.

The web site has been designed considering the alignment to the defined visual identity and includes the main recommendations for the best user experience, considering accessibility, web browsing facilities, security, or content organization.

The RAMONES site is expected to attract not only the general public, but also stakeholders with an interest in radioactivity studies, and on underwater science or hardware/ICT fields>It will thus constitute an important source of information, including contents for expert and non-expert audiences.

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The contents will be available in the most appropriate format (formatted text, leaflets, brochures, whitepapers, news, reports, multimedia, links, etc.) according to the scope and the target. Academic and technical audiences (such as scientific communities, research centers, developers, or public institutions) will have the opportunity to benefit from the material published, as well as stakeholders of other European projects to identify synergies and potential lines of collaboration. Journalists will find updated information, such as news, events or press releases. To boost these media, the website also includes a blog corner, as well as useful direct links to social media platforms.

In addition, the consortium and other interested and supporting stakeholders can use their own communication channels to ensure a wider dissemination and promotion of the RAMONES project among their ranks and collaborative networks. RAMONES will provide links to facilitate this dissemination. The website will be linked to and from the partners' website and relevant scientific communities.

The design and development of RAMONES portal is presented in a specific deliverable belonging to the same WP5. For more information, the document "D5.23 Website, Social Media" is available.

Figure 2. RAMONES website (home page).

In the Top Head and Main Menu sections of the web page, the contents organized by type (Home, About, Advisory Board, Consortium, News, Synergies, The Approach, Environmental Intelligence, Training, Events and Publications) are presented.

4.2.2 Social media channels

Social media channels allow reaching out to relevant groups through disseminating information about news, achievements, or any relevant event in an easy and quick way. Likewise, it also allows to consolidate groups of common interests in research, empowering networking, and relationships between many teams at international level.

Accessible to anyone that can be interested in RAMONES, the social platforms additionally address innovators, researchers, all relevant targeted groups. A task of follower's attraction will be carried out during the whole life of the project.

The social channels considered are LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. To make it easy to find and brand the project, all of them have a common name (**ramones_eu** or **ramones_eu_project**) and are aligned to the project identity principles.

1. LinkedIn

The official LinkedIn account of RAMONES is **RAMONES_EU project**, and a portion of the home page is presented below.

Figure 3. RAMONES LinkedIn group.

2. Twitter

An official account for RAMONES has been created on twitter: **ramones_eu**.

The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 4. RAMONES account on Twitter.

3. Facebook

RAMONES official account on Facebook is **Ramones EU**, and the home page is shown in the following figure.

Figure 5. RAMONES account on Facebook.

4. YouTube

An official channel for RAMONES has been created on YouTube: **project ramones_eu**

The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 6. RAMONES channel for YouTube.

5. Instagram

An official account for RAMONES has been created on Instagram: **ramones_eu**

The next figure shows the home page.

Figure 7. RAMONES account on Instagram.

4.3 Dissemination

4.3.1 Broad range

Press releases

The press releases offer general purpose announcements and publications to the public disseminated via web site as well as electronic and printed press. This media aims to reach the widest possible audience (general public, funders and other not connected stakeholders).

Figure 8. RAMONES samples of dissemination material.

Articles

Articles of general interest that may be distributed over the press, other media sites or the website of the project, including project news, collaborations, outputs, or achievements. The objective is to reach the general public, related initiatives, research groups or technology providers.

Hardcopy, materials, and gadgets

Print materials such as brochures, leaflets, cards, posters, briefing papers, or in the form of different kinds of gadgets that present general aspects of the project work. The goal is to strengthen project identification, consolidate engagement and to arouse the interest of the project among the most varied public. Its application will focus on face-to-face meetings, conferences, fairs, and exhibitions for various audiences.

Some examples of the hardcopy that are considered to be produced are shown in Figure 8.

4.3.2 Ecosystem

Dissemination at ecosystem range considers any audience involved at any level or any depth with the RAMONES' world, such as, for example, the academic or research fields, scientific or ICT context, or the above-mentioned stakeholders. This line of communication complements and expands the contents exposed widely and is backed-up by them (mainly by means of the website and the digital social media channels). The dissemination is led by the OTF, with the participation of technical partners for content production.

The main channels include both publications and events and collaboration.

Publications

Some types of documents and channels are presented to perform the dissemination activities about RAMONES. All documents will be hosted on the RAMONES website and properly announced by means of Publications, News sections and social media channels.

The presented below are considered as the main ones.

1. Newsletters

Periodic publications with an assembly of progresses in the project and related context (e.g. EOSC hub), mainly for EU H2020, research and innovation, and EOSC ecosystem and research groups. The newsletter production will be designed by the Outreach Task Force (OTF) with the collaboration of all project members according to their area of expertise.

2. Mailing

The main channels for dissemination are the digital channels and web, so we can keep and offer the communication track in an easy way. Additionally, an e-mailing service with potential additional content that notifies interested parties about progress of work of the project, mainly for targeted groups with interests (GDPR compliance required).

A mailing list is also available for project members (ramones@lists.uoa.gr).

3. Technical and general blog posts

Targeted extracts technical achievements of the project that can attract the interest of specific audiences, disseminated via the project's web site and social media, or included in the project's newsletters. Addressed to the general public, technology groups, scientific groups.

4. Whitepapers and research publications

White papers that expose experiences, lessons learnt and best practices in several key areas of the project. It considers research publications in international top-rank journals and conferences in diverse fields that span Physics, Chemistry, Geology, Environment, Marine Science, Robotics, Computer Science, Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Business Analytics, Remote Sensing, Geosciences, Natural Hazards, Radiation, and Ecology. Addressed to Targeted interest groups in research, business, and technology and more.

5. Multimedia material

Material consisting of slideshows, videos, or webcasts, presenting the services and their benefits disseminated via the project web site as well as social media. Addressed to research groups, technology providers.

Events and collaboration

Events and collaborative initiatives are key instruments to perform the RAMONES dissemination activities. All the events will be promoted on the RAMONES website and properly announced through the Events section and the social channels to get the maximum interest by the ecosystem, target audience and any other potential audience. Once the event is carried out, this will be announced also with the main contents and results both on the web and the social media channels.

The following are considered the main ones.

1. Event organization (Conferences/Workshops)

Organization of 6 general and/or open workshops/conferences bringing together all stakeholders for the exchange of knowledge and information and evaluating the work performed, and at least support of 14 workshops focusing on specific areas of project activities (from research, business, or technology) and several smaller scale workshops with stakeholders of interest.

2. Capacity Building

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Webinars on SMEs, industry, or researchers, bringing together those actors for raising awareness, training, assessment and feedback acquisition. Addressed to researchers and innovation stakeholders.

3. Fairs, Demos, Exhibitions

Participation in fairs and exhibitions by commercial partners presenting the business perspective of the project and its outcomes, backed-up with hardcopy material for dissemination and engagement purposes.

Preliminary considerations include the presence of the project with material and demonstrators in several exhibition areas, such as Oceanology International (<https://www.oceanologyinternational.com/>) and Ocean Business (<https://www.oceanbusiness.com/>). These major events which will be targeted by the project will be useful to engage public authorities and other urban stakeholders, including research, service providers and industry: ICRP International Conference Series, ENVIRA Conference Series, Applied Nuclear Physics Conference Series, IAEA Conference and Workshop Series, NEA/OECD Workshops, OpenAIRE - Nexus Public Launch Event, Blue Research and Innovation Days Week Smart City Expo World Congress, FIWARE Global Summit, IoT Week, EU Sustainable Energy Week, Zoom Smart Cities, EU Week of Regions and Cities, IoT Solutions World Congress.

4. Scientific publications/ presentations

Scientific publications in a journal or conference proceedings, including preprints, posters, and presentations. Addressed to researchers, academic audience, other research and innovation stakeholders.

5. Collaborations

Meetings and exchanges of information with established collaborators such as projects and initiatives. Addressed to stakeholders of European projects in RAMONES' research fields and Environmental Intelligence domain.

6. Datathons and Hackathons

Datathons and hackathons will be organized in collaboration with other entities (innovation hubs, academic and research organizations, or business clusters) and will attract innovators from research and business areas, software designers, students, mentors, and funders. Addressed to innovators and researchers, students, startups.

7. Project Meetings

Project meetings will act as a communication and innovation triggering event that will be used to mobilize all partner task forces but will also be used to introduce external actors to the project through targeted invitations from external audiences.

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The following is a group photo captured during RAMONES project inaugural Kick-Off meeting which was held virtually due to the pandemic restrictions on Monday 22nd and Tuesday 23rd of March 2021:

Figure 9. RAMONES group photo captured during the project's inaugural Kick-off meeting.

4.3.3 Project resources for partners

As a main element of dissemination and communication, a set of documents have been designed and others will be designed in the near future in order to be used by the consortium members. The goal is to always have available digital content for different purposes, both for new developments and for final uses. These document templates have already been provided and will be updated for the whole life of the project according to the needs and will be available in the most appropriate platform according to the type of use.

The following are considered as a first batch:

Table 3. Digital resources for project partners.

Resource	Description
Word document template	Preformatted document with initial structure and look & feel as well (including pictures, tables, headings, etc.) to facilitate the development of any RAMONES related

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	<p>document. The structure met the needs of project deliverables but can be also suitable with adaptations to other RAMONES publications (whitepapers, articles, etc.).</p> <p>This document is designed for project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.</p>
PowerPoint document template	<p>Preformatted document with initial structure and look & feel as well (including pictures, tables, headings, etc.) to facilitate the development of any RAMONES related presentation.</p> <p>The template also includes the promotion of RAMONES web site and the digital social platforms.</p> <p>This document is designed for the project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.</p>
Bare Brochure	<p>Executive presentation with RAMONES goals, services, and benefits.</p> <p>This document will be designed for the project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.</p>
Brochures and leaflets	<p>Executive presentations with RAMONES goals, services, and benefits.</p> <p>These documents are designed for a general audience and will be downloadable from the web site.</p>

The first two categories of documents are available on RAMONES common space online (GDrive > RAMONES > Supplementary).

As an example, a slide of the kick-off meeting presentation is depicted below, which includes the logo and all the design lines of the project.

As a word document sample, this deliverable itself is an example.

Figure 10. RAMONES template for presentation (first page).

4.4 Outreach

Outreach activities according to the EU definition are meant to engage a large audience and to bring knowledge and expertise on a particular topic to the general public – in our case primarily the measurement and monitoring of radioactivity levels in deep sea due to natural and anthropogenic activities.

Outreach activities can take several forms, such as class presentations, public and targeted workshops, public talks, etc. The main objective of outreach is to explain the benefits of research to a larger public (primarily the taxpayers who fund the research via the EU call and respective funding). Outreach implies an interaction between the sender and the receiver of the message, there is an engagement and a two-way communication and thus the new (social media platforms are meant to be more appropriate than the older communication instruments that tend to be one-way systems (like a broadcast or an advertisement)

It is common belief throughout RAMONES consortium that the steps described in the previous section are interactive and 2-way in nature and thus will suffice to guarantee the appropriate levels of outreach; nevertheless, more targeted, and broader public activities will follow that are expected to engage a broader public and to that end further sponsorship from governmental agencies may be sought to support further these activities especially school visits and exhibitions in public fora.

4.5 Engagement & Exploitation

Public engagement implies establishing participatory multi-actor dialogues and exchanges to foster mutual understanding, co-create research and innovation outcomes, and provide input to policy agendas. It is about bringing together researchers, policy makers, industry, and citizens, to deliberate on matters of science and technology. Public engagement also creates the space for ethical value-laden issues to be explored, while bringing inclusiveness, transparency, diversity, and creativity into the research and innovation process.

Public engagement processes allow different groups to establish a common language, arrive at joint understandings, learn from each other, explore controversies, and co-create ideas, knowledge, or solutions. To have the greatest impact, public engagement needs to be designed as a two-way process with feedback loops, so that the outcomes of the engagement processes are usefully fed back into the research and innovation process. We aspire to achieve public engagement through the series of activities described in sections 4.3 and 4.4

On the other hand, exploitation in general terms involves the utilization of results in further research activities other than those strictly covered and prescribed in the project. It also often involves developing, creating, and marketing a product, service, a process, or standardization activities. These latter activities in general can be commercial, societal, political, and/or for improving public knowledge. Project partners can exploit results themselves, or facilitate exploitation by others via making results available under open licenses:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

In the RAMONES context, since the project is both ambitious and risky, the technologies and applications of the technologies to be developed will raise public and industry interest, and thus we expect early additional interest from various policy makers, stakeholders and the general public that might want to have a first experience of our new innovative technologies.

As a step in this direction, a special brainstorming day within the consortium once a year is proposed to assess such opportunities and refine RAMONES engagement and exploitation strategy. Nevertheless, RAMONES initial stance would be that - with the caveat that the IP remains within the consortium, to engage in discussion of potential exploitation schemes that are compatible with our EU funding. This will be fully aligned with the RAMONES deliverable related to IP issues, D6.2 *"Data management plan, Innovation and IPR Management"*.

4.6 Content generation

The creation of content must be in accordance with the target and the media. As a rule, the following must be met:

4.6.1 Face-to-face presentations

Face-to-face events (meetings, hackathons, datathons, expositions, etc.) must be guided by the general principles and good communication practices. In any case, each exposition may contain five main sets:

- Presentation. With the welcome of the attendees and the organization.
- Introduction. An explanation of the RAMONES project in general lines (mainly context, goals, and scope) for locating the public and the goals of the event. This introduction must be short and attractive to attendees to improve their attention.
- Development. This is the main section of the conference or workshop, with the main development of the topic. It is suggested to mix the theoretical concepts with some examples to get the best understanding from the audience.
- Conclusion. In this section the speaker must remark the main concepts of the exposition, it is recommended to be brief.
- Closing. The final part when the speaker ends his presentation.

One RAMONES generic presentation is also scheduled for public use. Depending on the type of event, feedback requesting and interactivity from the audience can be valuable and useful.

In any case, it is necessary to inform the public beforehand about the topic, the goal, and any logistics of the event to boost the interest of the audience.

4.6.2 Digital channels

Digital channels are aimed at both promoting and storing the RAMONES news and contents. All public material will be published on the web site, which in fact acts as a content hub. Additionally, other online channels such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube are also worthy of reaching out to a wide range of short messages that inform them about news and allow them to find more information in our portal.

4.6.3 Contents of general purpose

Any general-purpose document (such as newsletters, press releases, leaflets, executive presentations, etc.) is led by the Outreach Task Force with the support of the WP5 partners

involved in and the final validation of the Project Management Board. These documents may use any kind of content coming from other contributions to the RAMONES scope (for instance, deliverables or specific developments may be a baseline for a newsletter) or may be specifically developed for a specific target (for instance, the promotion of an event).

4.6.4 Contents of technical and scientific purpose

The technical contents (such as whitepapers, scientific or technical contributions, webinars, code development and integrations, connections with others research lines, etc.) are defined, developed, and reviewed by the responsible technical or scientific partner of the relevant work package. Every partner will be responsible for the content, accuracy, and correctness of every post.

4.7 Instruments per line of activity

Although all the channels can be applied for more than one line of activity (communication, dissemination, engagement, and outreach), the following dedications are mainly estimated, as presented in Grant Agreement:

4.7.1 Communication instruments

The communication activities target raising awareness about both the project and its results and even reach the general public, beyond the main stakeholders identified by the project, however with proportionally smaller effort dedicated to such an audience. Many of the instruments employed for communications have a dual nature and can be utilized also for dissemination purposes, while the reverse may also apply indirectly. Several, relatively low cost, instruments that will be employed towards achieving the project communication objectives, are presented in the following:

- hardcopy materials, gadgets;
- articles;
- press releases;
- blog posts;
- multimedia content;
- media extracts;
- e-mail;
- newsletter;
- social media posts.

4.7.2 Dissemination instruments

Dissemination instruments can use communication instruments, yet build upon specializing their use, while employing additional specialized instruments tailored to dissemination objectives.

The main channels are listed below:

- technical blog posts;
- whitepapers;
- multimedia material;
- workshops and capacity building;
- fairs, demos and exhibitions;
- scientific publications / presentations;
- collaborations;
- project meetings;
- datathons and hackathons;
- social media channels.

As mentioned above, dissemination instruments can also be useful for communication purposes.

4.8 Cross promotion

Each channel is also useful to promote others, presenting them all before the audience as a homogenous unit of work, following the principles of project identity. So that, the following rules are applied:

1. The website as a main point of reference of any contact point.
The website also offers different channels (“Get in touch” section and social media) to contact and be updated, as depicted below:

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Figure 11. RAMONES “Get in touch” section of the website.

2. All the channels offer access to the web site for additional information. The link from Facebook account is shown as an example:

Figure 12. RAMONES Facebook account with the connection to RAMONES website.

3. All the document templates include the reference to the site and the social channels. As an example, the last slide of the kick-off meeting presentation is depicted below:

Figure 13. RAMONES presentation in Kick-Off Meeting with references to social channels.

4. The RAMONES web and channels are also promoted from the partners and other policy makers and stakeholders' channels. Some examples are depicted below:

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iseedproject.eu/environmental-intelligence

Home About Consortium News and Events Project Results Gallery Environmental Intelligence

Towards a blueprint for Environmental Intelligence

I-Seed is part of a collaboration agreement signed among the H2020 EIC Pathfinder/FET Proactive funded projects: I-Seed, WATCHPLANT, SMARTLAGOON, RAMONES, and ReSET. The main aim of this collaboration is to deliver a blueprint for a full-fledged system for Environmental Intelligence.

Environmental Intelligence cross-projects collaboration initiatives

Figure 14. RAMONES reference from a FET partner's website (project I-Seed).

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cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101017808

European Commission | CORDIS | EU research results

English EN

HOME RESULTS PACKS RESEARCH*EU MAGAZINES NEWS & EVENTS PROJECTS & RESULTS ABOUT US LOG IN

HORIZON 2020

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Fact Sheet Results

Objective

Natural radioactivity in the marine environment has been present since the Earth's formation, while artificial radionuclides were introduced into the oceans in 1944. More recent direct sources exist that feed the oceans, such as low-level liquid discharges from reprocessing plants, large-scale releases due to disasters (e.g. Fukushima hit by the tsunami in 2011), and smaller-scale radiological events. Exploration of submarine environments should consider the existence of radioactivity in terms of its short- and long-term impact on marine and coastal ecosystems, also in correlation to natural hazards, such as seismic activity over submarine faults. Significantly undersampled in oceans, radioactivity poses real risks to marine ecosystems and human population, urging for detailed, data-driven modelling.

RAMONES aims to offer new and efficient solutions for in situ, continuous, long-term monitoring of radioactivity in harsh subsea environments. A new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by SoA robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) will be developed towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data towards shaping new policies and guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health.

The main ambition is to lay a radical new path to close the existing marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and

Project Information

RAMONES
Grant agreement ID: 101017808

Status
Ongoing project

Start date
1 January 2021

End date
31 December 2024

Funded under
H2020-EU.1.2.2.

Overall budget
€ 3 926 093,75

EU contribution
€ 3 926 093,75

Figure 15. RAMONES reference from CORDIS Europe.

ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/news/five-eu-projects-join-forces-develop-environmental-intelligence-system

An official website of the European Union How do you know?

What is Horizon 2020 ?

Five EU projects join forces to develop an Environmental Intelligence system

Tuesday, 2 February, 2021

#H2020
#H2020

The collaboration agreement between 5 EIC Pathfinder/FET Proactive projects has been signed. Its main aim is to deliver a blueprint for a full-fledged system for environmental intelligence.

The main goal of Environmental Intelligence call (FETPROACT-ESC-08-2020) is to build a systemic understanding of the socio-environmental inter-relationships, to regulate or design policies and incentives for environmental sustainability and to track their effectiveness over time and to provide intelligible options for adjusting them. Moreover, the call was designed as a joint initiative in creating a European strategy for Environmental Intelligence system.

In the 2020 call, a total of 87 proposals were submitted. Out of them, 5 gained support under the EIC Pathfinder (FET Proactive) funding scheme: I-Seed, RAMONES, ReSET, SMARTLAGOON and WATCHPLANT.

I-Seed focuses on monitoring of environmental parameters in topsoil, air and their interface. Its aim is to develop a new generation of self-deployable and biodegradable soft miniaturized robots, inspired by the morphology and dispersion abilities of plant seeds.

RAMONES aims to propose new and efficient solutions for in situ, continuous, long-term monitoring of radioactivity in harsh subsea environments. It will design, develop and validate a new generation of radiation-sensing instruments to perform spectroscopic studies.

Figure 16. RAMONES reference from European Commission site in Horizon 2020-Environmental Intelligence section.

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Figure 17. RAMONES reference from the Blue Research & Innovation Days site.

These channels are promoted from the web site, as can be seen in the next image:

Figure 18. In the RAMONES website the Synergies section offers a connection to other projects' sites.

4.9 Targeted communication for possible exploitation of the business sector

It is anticipated great interest in the RAMONES project and its results. It is also anticipated to build the technology and the deployment pipeline that will allow operational rapid response.

Applications will range from waste disposal, volcanic activity, deep sea drilling, nuclear plant decommissions etc. and as such there will be interest from public and private bodies. Special linking and engagement activities will be introduced during the project lifetime to sequentially measure the business potential.

5. Organization

5.1 Coordination Model

The Outreach Task Force is created to lead and coordinate the RAMONES Dissemination activities. The composition of the OTF is based on the Grant Agreement, and is led by the Outreach Manager (Konstantinos Nikolopoulos, UDUR) and engages partners with key roles in outreach WP.

In WP5 all project members participate and especially the ones who are requested to contribute with their knowledge and networking, as well as with specific tasks in charge.

To define the contribution to each KPIs achievement, the following methodology will be applied:

Figure 19. Dissemination and KPIs assignments process.

- KPI: presentation of all the KPIs already proposed in the Grant Agreement which will define the project achievements.
- Target Value: quantification of each KPI.
- NKUA Monitoring: monitoring of the process by the project coordinator
- Partner share and support: assignment of the contribution of each partner to each KPI, according to its field of knowledge and activity and support from other partners.
- Coordinated Action Plan: tasks to be developed for each partner.

5.2 Key Performance Indicator

The strategy, as stated above, will be mainly based on the concept of Key Performance Indicator (KPI). KPIs are generally used to evaluate either the success of a particular activity or progress towards the project's goals. Choosing the right KPIs is important for the project. Although both qualitative and quantitative indicators can be used, quantitative indicators are generally preferred since they can give better insights into the project. Success indicator with each KPI will help to evaluate the success criteria for that particular KPI. The KPIs presented by this deliverable will be highly oriented towards the nature of the dissemination activities.

The following KPIs are considered, organized accordingly to its main objective, considering its scope (wide range or ecosystem) and the target value:

1. KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction:

Table 4. KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction.

Range	KPI	Target Value
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized	6
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panelists on project specific topics	14

2. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Table 5. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination.

Range	KPI	Target Value
Broad range	Average technical blog posts per year	2
Broad range	Templates for dissemination activities and other material	2
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	10
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artefacts	120
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	50

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Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	3
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	8
Ecosystem	Percentage of Open Access publications	>70%
Broad range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	3
Broad range	Commercial exploitation events participation	5

3. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Table 6. KPIs concerning communication activities success indicators.

Range	KPI	Target Value
Wide range	Websites launched (work plan)	1
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	monthly
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	4
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	3
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	10.000
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	1200
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	2
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per year	6
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	8
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	8

4. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Table 7. KPIs concerning strengthening impact via joint efforts.

Range	KPI	Target Value
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & research infrastructures liaised with RAMONES (total)	6
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties	5
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	2
Ecosystem	3rd party Datathons/hackathons supported by the project	2
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	200
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	1800

5.3 Roles

Outreach Task Force (OTF): the Outreach task force is led by Outreach Manager and engages partners with key roles in outreach Work Packages (mainly WP5). The role of the team is to monitor outreach activities, identify opportunities and mobilize resources, as outreach in RAMONES is quite intensive, ambitious and of strategic importance for the success of the project.

5.4 Monitoring and Evaluation

5.4.1 Digital channels

The web page will be regularly updated. Moreover, the effectiveness of the web page will be periodically analyzed by means of Google Analytics tool. This will allow reports to run on the website, giving a very clear picture of information such as:

- Users count visiting the website and visit time.
- Languages and locations of visitors.
- Devices used for browsing the website.

The following images are an example of website analytics.

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Figure 20. RAMONES website tracking (example 1).

Figure 21. RAMONES website tracking (example 2).

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The social channels will also be periodically tracked by means of embedded tools in each platform.

Following an example from Facebook account, tracking the impressions among others KPIs (similar are applied for the others social networks):

Figure 22. RAMONES Facebook account: tracking facilities (example 1).

Figure 23. RAMONES Facebook account: tracking facilities (example 2).

5.4.2 Physical channels

The tracking from physical channels (meetings, published articles, connections with other projects, events hosted and attendees, etc.) will be collected by the Outreach Task Force for

each specific action and monthly updated and shared Internally via the shared workspace, analyzing the level of fulfillment and trends, being useful for the committed project reports.

The Outreach task force is led by Outreach Manager, Konstantinos Nikolopoulos, WP5 leader and engages mainly partners with key roles in outreach Work Packages (mainly WP5), that is NKUA, UDUR, IST-ID and NTUA representatives. The members of every partner representative in the Outreach Task Force will be finalized in the first PEC meeting.

5.4.3 Reporting models

A set of templates for reporting dissemination will be created, according to each kind of publication. The content of each one will meet the needs of any specific kind of action.

1. Scientific publications:
 - Type of scientific publication (article in a Journal, publication in conference proceedings / workshops, books/ chapter in books, thesis/dissertation, others).
 - Title of scientific publication.
 - Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
 - ISSN or eSSN.
 - Author(s).
 - Title of the journal or equivalent.
 - Number/ date.
 - Publisher.
 - Place of publication.
 - Year of public action.
 - Pages.
 - Public & private publication.
 - Peer view.
 - Is/will open access provided to this publication.
2. General publications (press releases, videos, campaigns etc.):
 - Type of publication (press release, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications, flyers, social media, website, communication campaign, video/film, others).
 - Title of publication.
 - Author(s)/ creator (s).
 - Title of the journal or equivalent.
 - Date of publication.
 - Publisher - Partner.
 - Place of publication.
 - Public & private publication.
 - Is/Will open access provided to this publication.
 - Other relevant comments.

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3. Dissemination and communication activities:
 - Type of dissemination and communication activities (organization of a conference, organization of a workshop, project presentations, exhibition, training, participation to a conference/ a workshop/ or other event, brokerage/ pitch/ trade fair, others).
 - Title of activity.
 - Short description.
 - Website/ social media (if available).
 - Type of audience.
 - Number of attendees.
 - Date of the activity.
 - Place of the activity.
 - Partner participants (name, affiliation).
 - Presentation if applicable.
 - Is/will open access provided to this publication.
 - Other comments.
4. Dissemination and communication results:
 - Type of audience reached in the context of all dissemination & communication activities (multiple choices are possible among science community/ higher education, research, industry, civil society, general public, policy makers, media, investors, others).
 - Estimated number of persons reached.

6. Planning

Project starting date is the launch of official RAMONES dissemination activities, including the generation of templates and the organization of relative committees.

6.1 Deliverables of Communication, Dissemination

The deliverables of this Work Package are detailed below, specifying their codification, title and description:

- D5.3 Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach & Engagement Plan
- D5.4 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities
- D5.5 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach
- D5.6 Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities

6.2 Deliverables Planning

Finally, the scheduling for deliverables is presented in the following table:

Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan

Table 8. Dissemination planning.

Code	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Month
D5.3	Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach & Engagement Plan	UDUR	Report	Public	4
D5.4	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities	NKUA	Report	Public	12, 24, 36, 48
D5.5	Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach	NKUA	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	8, 18
D5.6	Report on Outreach and Liaison Activities	UDUR	Report	Public	24, 48

6.3 Timeline

The timeline of RAMONES deliverables related to dissemination activities and their due dates is depicted below.

Figure 24. Timeline of RAMONES deliverables related to dissemination activities.